

Kinetics of the Anation of *cis*-Diaqua-bis(biguanide)cobalt(III) by Glutamic Acid in Mixed Ethanol-Water Media

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Kinetics of anation of *cis*-diaqua-bis(biguanide)cobalt(III) ion by glutamic acid (LH) have been determined in mixed ethanol-water media. The low values of ΔH^\ddagger together with quite large negative values of ΔS^\ddagger are indicative of an associative interchange mechanism (I_a). The effect of solvent variation on rate also supports I_a mechanism.

Mechanism of substitution at octahedral cobalt(III) complexes has been a subject of continued interest. Various evidences suggest that the anation reaction of octahedral cobalt(III) mainly proceeds via dissociative interchange¹ process (I_d), though associative interchange (I_a) process^{2,3} is not rare. The mechanism depends mainly on the nature of the systems and other experimental parameters. In response to the above mechanistic uncertainties, we studied the titled reaction.

Results and Discussion

Effect of varying [Complex 1] on rate : The rate of the reaction was measured at 490 nm which is the absorption maximum for both 1 and the product and where a substantial difference exists between substrate and product complex (2) at a fixed excess of glutamic acid, pH, ionic strength and temperature. The reaction followed first order kinetics,

$$d[(2)]/dt = k_{\text{obs}} [(1)] \quad (1)$$

Effect of varying pH on rate constant : At a fixed [complex 1] (5×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³), [LH] (5×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³), ionic strength (0.5 mol dm⁻³) and temperature (45°), the k_{obs} ($\times 10^5$) values were found to be 5.5, 6.1, 7.1, 8.3, 10.0 s⁻¹ corresponding to pHs 3.0, 3.3, 3.6, 3.9, 4.2 respectively, in 10% (v/v) ethanol-water. The enhancement of rate with increase in pH can be explained by considering the equilibria,

The pK_a value³ of the above equilibria is 6 at 25°. With increase in pH the percentage of the hydroxo-aqua species in solution is increased and the reactivity of the hydroxo-aqua complex is usually higher than that of the diaqua complex due to the well known⁴ labilizing effect of the coordinated hydroxide ion. Thus the effect of

change in pH can be partly accounted for. On the other hand, glutamic acid (LH) dissociates as

The pK_1 , pK_2 and pK_3 values⁵ are 2.39, 4.29 and 9.54 respectively at 25°.

The effect of hydrogen ion concentration on k_{obs} can be explained in terms of equilibrium (2) for which the rate expression can be given by

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_1 + k_2 K_a [\text{H}^+]^{-1} \quad (6)$$

where k_1 is the observed rate constant when the reacting species is the diaqua complex and k_2 is the observed rate constant for the hydroxo-aqua complex. Plot of k_{obs} versus $[\text{H}^+]^{-1}$ is linear. Within the experimental pH range, the incoming ligand exists predominantly in the zwitterionic form.

Effect of varying [ligand] on rate : At a fixed [complex 1] (5×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³), ionic strength (0.5 mol dm⁻³) and pH (3.6), the [ligand] was varied in the range 5×10^{-2} to 15×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³ at four different temperatures in three different ethanol-water media (10, 20, 30%, v/v). The k_{obs} values increased with increasing [ligand] tending to a limiting value (Fig. 1) due to the formation of an outer sphere complex. The results are collected in Table 1. The following reaction scheme is proposed from the experimental findings.

Fig. 1. Variation of k_{obs} with $[LH]$ at different temperatures in 10% (v/v) ethanol-water media; $[Complex\ 1] = 5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $pH = 4.0$, ionic strength = 0.5 mol dm^{-3} : (A) 45° , (B) 50° and (C) 55° .

TABLE 1—VALUES OF $10^4 k_{obs} \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$ AT DIFFERENT $[LH]$ IN DIFFERENT ETHANOL-WATER MEDIA AND AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

$pH = 3.6$, ionic strength = $5 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Co(BigH)_2(H_2O)_2]^{3+} = 5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

Temp. $^\circ C$	EtOH % (v/v)	$[LH] \times 10^2 \text{ (mol dm}^{-3}\text{)}$				
		5.0	7.5	10.0	12.5	15.0
45	10	0.72	0.90	1.00	1.20	1.32
	20	1.02	1.20	1.60	1.82	1.90
	30	1.20	1.42	1.70	2.00	2.18
50	10	0.92	1.16	1.32	1.60	1.80
	20	1.28	1.60	1.90	2.20	2.50
	30	1.50	1.78	2.30	2.58	2.80
55	10	1.16	1.48	1.70	2.00	2.32
	20	1.60	2.00	2.40	2.72	2.70
	30	1.80	2.20	2.80	3.20	3.42
60	10	1.42	1.80	2.20	2.60	2.90
	20	1.90	2.40	2.88	3.22	3.60
	30	2.24	2.60	3.40	3.90	4.10

From the above Scheme, the following rate law is derived:

$$d[(2)]/dt = k_a K_E [(1)]_T [LH]/(1 + K_E[LH]) \quad (7)$$

where, $[(1)]_T$ is the total coccentration of the unreacted complex, K_E the outersphere association constant, and k_a the anation rate constant. Therefore,

$$\text{Rate} = k_{obs} [(1)]_T \quad (8)$$

$$\text{where, } k_{obs} = k_a K_E [\text{ligand}]/(1 + K_E [\text{ligand}]) \quad (9)$$

$$\text{or, } 1/k_{obs} = 1/k_a + 1/k_a K_E [\text{ligand}] \quad (10)$$

A plot of $1/k_{obs}$ versus $1/[\text{ligand}]$ is a straight-line at all temperatures studied. The least-squares slopes and intercepts give the values of $1/k_a K_E$ and $1/k_a$. The k_a values are collected in Table 2, and K_E values are found to be within 8.5 to $9.5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ range. An analogous system is cited in the same table for comparison. Results clearly reflect the dependence of reaction rate on the participating ligand, favouring an associative interchange mechanism.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF $10^4 k_a \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$ AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES IN DIFFERENT ETHANOL-WATER MEDIA

$pH = 3.6$, ionic strength = $5 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

EtOH % (v/v)	45°	50°	55°	60°
$[Co(BigH)_2(H_2O)_2]^{3+} + \text{Aspartic acid}^a$:				
10	12.0			
20	12.8			
30	13.3			
$[Co(BigH)_2(H_2O)_2]^{3+} + \text{Glutamic acid}^b$:				
10	2.10(0.21)	3.12(0.41)	4.20(0.50)	5.2(0.53)
20	3.20(0.66)	4.30(0.42)	5.10(0.34)	6.2(0.38)
30	3.50(0.44)	4.90(0.73)	6.25(0.81)	7.2(1.32)

^aRef. 3. ^bPresent work.

Values in the parenthesis reflect the SD against each k_a .

Effect of varying ionic strength on rate: At a fixed $[complex\ 1]$ ($5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), $[ligand]$ ($5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), pH (3.6) and at 45° , the $10^5 k_{obs}$ values are 7.20, 7.21 and 7.25 s^{-1} at different ionic strengths of 0.3, 0.4 and 0.5 mol dm^{-3} ($NaClO_4$) respectively, in 10% (v/v) ethanol-water. The rate is thus found to be independent of ionic strength as evidenced from Bronsted-Bjerrum equation that suggests that the reaction between an ion and a neutral molecule should be independent of ionic strength⁶.

Effect of varying temperature on rate: The anation of cobalt(III) complex has been studied at four different temperatures with different $[ligand]$. The values of the rate constants for the interchange process are given in Table 1. Activation parameters (ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger) were evaluated from the Eyring plot and compared with another system (Table 3). The low values of ΔH^\ddagger along-

TABLE 2—VISCOSITY *A*- AND *B*-COEFFICIENTS OF DRUG SALTS AT THREE DIFFERENT TEMPERATURE IN H₂O

Drug	<i>A</i> (dm ^{3/2} mol ^{1/2})*		<i>B</i> (dm ³ mol ⁻¹)**		
	<i>A</i> _{Theor}	<i>A</i> _{exp}	293 K	298 K	303 K
Cyproheptadine hydrochloride	0.0087	0.0087	2.280 (2.450)	2.012 (2.167)	1.707 (1.752)
Chlorpromazine hydrochloride	0.0081	0.0075	1.320 (1.412)	1.169 (1.279)	1.136 (1.144)
Ethambutol dihydrochloride	0.0066	0.0125	2.437 (2.824)	2.178 (2.393)	2.060 (2.154)
Amodiaquin dihydrochloride	0.0074	0.0075	1.946 (1.484)	1.709 (1.450)	1.601 (1.398)
Pheniramine maleate	—	0.0450	0.818 (0.363)	0.885 (0.390)	0.960 (0.429)

*At 298 K. **Values in parenthesis are from Vand's equation.

The viscosity data have been analyzed on the basis of a transition state treatment of the relative viscosity of electrolyte solutions as suggested by Feakins *et al.*¹¹. The *B*-coefficient is expressed by equation (6),

$$B = \frac{\bar{V}_1^0 - \bar{V}_2^0}{1000} + \frac{\bar{V}_1^0}{1000} \left(\frac{\Delta\mu_2^{0\ddagger} - \Delta\mu_1^{0\ddagger}}{RT} \right) \quad (6)$$

where \bar{V}_1^0 and \bar{V}_2^0 are the partial molar volumes of the solvent and solute respectively. $\Delta\mu_2^{0\ddagger}$ is the contribution per mole of solute to the Gibbs energy change of activation of viscous flow of the solution. $\Delta\mu_1^{0\ddagger}$, the Gibbs energy change of activation per mole of pure solvent, is given by

$$\Delta\mu_1^{0\ddagger} = \Delta G_1^{0\ddagger} = RT \ln \left(\frac{\eta_1 v_1}{hN} \right) \quad (7)$$

where V_1 is the molar volume of solvent, N the Avogadro number, and h the Planck constant.

The activation parameters for viscous flow for the electrolytes and pure solvent are presented in Table 3a. From the *B*-coefficient values at three different temperatures, the ionic activation entropy and enthalpy have been calculated from the equations,

$$\frac{(\Delta\mu^{0\ddagger})}{dT} = -\Delta S_2^{0\ddagger} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{and } \Delta H_2^{0\ddagger} = \Delta\mu_2^{0\ddagger} + T\Delta S_2^{0\ddagger} \quad (9)$$

The results are recorded in Table 3a. From the accurate density values of the solutions, apparent molar volumes, (ϕ_v) of the solutions have been calculated using the equation⁵,

$$\phi_v = \frac{1000}{C\rho_0}(\rho_0 - \rho) + \frac{M_2}{\rho_0} \quad (10)$$

The terms have their usual significance and M_2 is the

Fig. 3

TABLE 3a—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR VISCOUS FLOW

Water/Drug	Temp. K	$\Delta\mu^{0\ddagger}$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta H^{0\ddagger}$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$T\Delta S^{0\ddagger}$ kJ mol ⁻¹
H ₂ O	293	9.28		
	298	9.16	16.61	7.45
	303	9.03		
Cyproheptadine hydrochloride	293	356.60		
	298	326.49	2547.78	2221.29
	303	282.06		
Chlorpromazine hydrochloride	293	230.52		
	298	207.82	1171.25	963.43
	303	198.19		
Ethambutol dihydrochloride	293	365.01		
	298	329.68	1613.16	1283.48
	303	321.94		
Amodiaquin dihydrochloride	293	310.21		
	298	294.69	1355.57	1060.88
	303	274.61		
Pheniramine maleate	293	164.73	1055.00	876.12
	298	178.88		
	303	194.13		

formula weight of the solute. The partial molar volume at infinite dilution, (ϕ_v^0), have been obtained by fitting the results to the Masson equation¹²,

$$\phi_v = \phi_v^0 + S_v C^{1/2} \quad (11)$$

S_v is a constant dependent on charge and electrolyte type and can probably be related to ion-ion interactions in fairly concentrated solutions. In view of relative uncertainties in the experimental values at high and low temperatures, ϕ_v^0 values at 298 K should be regarded to be of greater accuracy and are presented in Table 4.

The relative viscosities of the salts have been found to be high indicating fairly strong attractive forces influencing the movement of the fluid. The *A*-values of

Complex 2. The pseudo-first order conditions was maintained throughout and the conventional mixing technique was adopted. The ionic strength of the reaction media was adjusted by recrystallized NaClO_4 . The pH of the reaction mixtures was adjusted by the addition of $\text{NaOH}/\text{HClO}_4$ with the help of a Systronics pH meter (accuracy $=\pm 0.01$). The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) were obtained by plotting $\log [D_{\infty}-D_0]/(D_{\infty}-D_t)$ against time, where D_{∞} , D_t and D_0 are the optical densities at infinite time, at time t and at the outset. The plots of $\log [D_{\infty}-D_0]/(D_{\infty}-D_t)$ versus time gave straight-lines passing through the origin. The linearity of the plots ruled out the possibility of any kind of consecutive reactions. A.R. grade chemicals, double-distilled water and ethanol were used. The temperature was controlled to within $\pm 0.1^\circ$. The rate constants represented as an average of duplicate are reproducible within $\pm 4\%$.

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